

Parent Support and Peer Influence as Predictors of Academic Adjustment of Student with Visual Impairment

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Abstract

This paper examined parental support and peer influence as predictor of academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Oyo State with the purpose of identifying the relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of students with visual impairment, investigate the joint contribution of parental support, peer influence on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment and to examine the relative contribution of parental support and peer influence of the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The sample consisted of 50 participants (32 males, 18 females) with visual impairment. Questionnaire method was use to collect data for the study. The data collected was analyzed using frequency count, percentages, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA). The study revealed that there was significant relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo state. The study recommends that educational institutions should foster collaborative relationships between parents and educators to promote academic adjustment among students with visual impairments. Regular meetings, progress reports, and parent-teacher conferences can facilitate open communication and ensure that parents are informed about their child's academic progress.

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Introduction

Students with visual impairment are confronted with series of challenges which significantly affect their academic adjustment. Adjustment is the extent at which an individual irrespective of their impairment, condition or status was able to maintain an alignment between himself or herself and the immediate environment or circumstance in order to be fit or function in such environment. Adjustment ranges from academic, psychological, social, medical, physical, emotional and a host of others (Abodunrin and Adelabu, 2025). The academic adjustment of students with visual impairment is a multifaceted process influenced by various social, psychological, and environmental factors. Parental support and peer influence play crucial roles in shaping the educational experiences and overall well-being of these students. The role of parents in providing emotional, financial, and educational support cannot be overstated, as they serve as primary caregivers and advocates for their children's academic success. At the same time, the influence of peers, both positive and negative, significantly affects the way students with visual impairment navigate their educational environment, impacting their motivation, confidence, and sense of belonging.

Abodunrin and Abodunrin (2020) observed that visual impairment is a condition characterized by deficiency in the organ of sight which hinders individual capability from performing certain function that requires the use of sight. Parental support plays a crucial role in the overall development of school age student. Part of the parental roles helps in developing the learning habit of their children as it helps in their academic adjustment. Such roles include; parents as parent, Parents as teacher, parents as educational decision makers and parents as advocate. (Turble,2003).

Adeyemo (2010) observed that a supportive family background plays an important role in the success and happiness especially students with visual impairment. Factors like parental educational background, income, exposure and family dynamic significantly impact the academic and social lives of these students. Family factors along with peer pressure can influence the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment making it important to investigate this aspect further. The academic adjustment of student with visual impairment is predetermined by their family life and peer influence (Abodunrin, Enweremadu and Edim (2024).

Parental support is one of the strongest factors of academic success for students with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairment. Parents serve as the first source of encouragement, helping their children develop self-esteem and resilience in the face of academic and social challenges. The level of involvement of parents in their child's education can significantly determine their academic adjustment. According to Turnbull, Turnbull, Wehmeyer, and Shogren (2019), parental involvement in the education of children with disabilities fosters higher levels of achievement and engagement. Parents who take an active role in their children's academic lives by providing resources, advocating for inclusive education, and working closely with teachers help create a supportive learning environment. This support includes providing assistive technologies such as screen readers, Braille materials, and audio resources, which are essential for students with visual impairment to access learning materials effectively.

Emotional support from parents is also a critical aspect of academic adjustment. Students with visual impairment may experience feelings of isolation, frustration, or anxiety due to their condition. In such situations, parental encouragement and reassurance provide a sense of security, allowing students to focus on their studies rather

than their limitations. A study by Hill and Tyson (2009) found that students who receive strong parental support tend to be more confident in their academic abilities and exhibit a higher level of perseverance when faced with academic difficulties. When parents provide consistent motivation, students develop a positive mindset toward their education, which in turn enhances their academic adjustment. Moreover, parents who actively engage in their children's education—by assisting with homework, attending school meetings, and advocating for their children's needs—create an environment that promotes learning readiness and academic success. A conducive home environment, characterized by positive attitudes and realistic expectations, also reinforces the child's ability to navigate academic and social challenges. Conversely, parental neglect, overprotectiveness, or a lack of understanding about the child's needs can hinder the development of autonomy, self-confidence, and academic resilience (Komolafe, 2016).

While parental support lays a strong foundation for academic success, peer influence is another crucial factor in the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. Peers play an essential role in shaping the social and academic experiences of students, influencing their attitudes, behaviors, and motivation. The presence of supportive peers can foster a sense of belonging and inclusion, which is fundamental to academic engagement. Students with visual impairment often face social challenges, including exclusion, bullying, or stereotyping, which can negatively impact their confidence and willingness to participate in academic activities. However, positive peer interactions create an inclusive learning environment where students with visual impairment feel accepted and valued. Peers significantly affect the social and academic experiences of students. For visually impaired students, positive peer relationships can enhance social integration, provide emotional support, and contribute to a sense of belonging within the school community.

Peer influence can manifest in various ways, including academic collaboration, emotional encouragement, and social integration. When students with visual impairment have friends who are willing to assist them with note-taking, reading, or navigating the school environment, they experience fewer barriers to learning. Research by Wentzel (2005) suggests that peer relationships significantly influence motivation and engagement, as students tend to mirror the behaviors and attitudes of their friends. If surrounded by academically driven peers, students with visual impairment are more likely to develop a positive attitude toward learning, thereby enhancing their academic adjustment.

The ability of an individual irrespective of their condition depends on their level of acceptability, recognition and accommodation, by their family and society at large. One of the important factors that better accept persons with visual impairment to adjust psychologically. Socially, emotionally and academically is concern with individual level of acceptability by their parent and other related factors (Abodunrin and Komolafe 2017).

This paper there for investigate parental support and peer influence as predictors of academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State.

Methods

The study adopted descriptive research design. A total of 50 participants including male and female students with visual impairment were purposively selected for the study. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the studies.

The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods:

- Descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, and mean) was used to analyze the demographic information.
- Inferential statistics, specifically Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC), was used to determine the relationships between parental support, peer influence, and academic adjustment among students with visual impairment.

Results

Analysis of Socio-Demographic Characteristic

Table 1. *Distribution of Age range*

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage
12 to 16years	10	20.0
17 to 21 years	12	24.0
22 to 26 years	28	56.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 1 reveals that 28 representing 56.0% of the respondents were between 22 to 26 years of Age while 12 (24.0%) were between 17 to 21 years and 10(20.0%) were between 12 to 16 years. Therefore the above result implies that majority of the respondents age were between 22 to 26years.

Table 2. *Distribution of gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	32	64.0
Female	18	36.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 shows number and frequency of gender that 32 representing 64.0% of the respondents were male and 18 (36.0%) were female. Therefore the above result implies that majority of respondents use for this study were male.

Table 3. *Distribution of Type of Vision Impaired*

Type of Vision Impaired	Frequency	Percentage
Partial	28	56.0
Totally	22	44.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3 shows number and frequency of type of vision Impaired that 28 representing 56.0% of the respondents were partial impaired 22 (44.0%) were totally impaired. Therefore the above result implies that majority of respondents were partial impaired use for this study.

Table 4. *Distribution of Onset of Impairment*

Onset of Impairment	Frequency	Percentage
Congenital	36	72.0
Acquired	14	28.0
Total	50	100.0

Table .4 shows number and frequency of Onset of Impairment that 36 representing 72.0% of the respondents were congenital while 14 (28.0%) were acquired. Therefore the above result implies that majority of respondents were congenital use for this study.

Answers to research questions

This section consists of the results from the inferential statistics on the account of the three questions raised and answered.

Research question 1: What is the relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of student living with visual impairment in Oyo state?

Table 5. *Descriptive Statistics and Correlation among the variables*

Variables	1	2	3
Academic –adjustment	1.000		
Parental support P<(0.05)	.584** .000	1.000	
Peer influence P<(0.05)	.810** .000	.753** .000	1.000
Mean	33.12	32.56	31.96
Standard Deviation	4.30	4.29	3.92

Table 5 shows Mean, Standard Deviation and zero order correlation among the variables. It was observed that there was significant relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of student living with visual impairment in Oyo State in the following order of magnitude: peer group influence ($r=0.810$, $p< 0.05$) and parental support ($r=0.584$, $p< 0.05$), has significant relationships with academic adjustment. It implies that there is significant the relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of student living with visual impairment in Oyo state

Research question 2: What is the joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State?

Table 6. Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the interactive effects of the Independent Variable on the Dependent Variable

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	597.267	2	298.633	44.984	.000 ^b
Residual	312.013	47	6.639		
Total	909.280	49			

R = .810^a
R² = .657
Adjusted R² = .642
Std. Error of the Estimate = 2.57655

*Denotes significant relationship at 0.06 significance level.

Table 6 shows that there is joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State is significant. The result yields a coefficient of multiple regressions $R = .810$; $R^2 = .657$ and adjusted R-square = 0.642. This suggests that these two factors combined account for 64.2% (Adj.R²= .642) variance in the prediction of academic adjustment. This implies that there is significant joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State. The other factors accounting for the remaining variance are beyond the scope of this study. The ANOVA result from the regression analysis shows that there is joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State ($F_{(2, 47)} = 44.984$; $P < 0.05$). This thus implies that there is significant joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State

Research question 3: What is the relative contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment with student with visual impairment in Oyo State?.

Table 7. Relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variables (Test of significance of the regression coefficients)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.083	3.128	-	1.625	.111
Parent support	.060	.130	.360	2.462	.040
Peer Support	.939	.143	.855	6.581	.000

Dependent Variable: academic adjustment; *Denotes significant at $P < 0.05$.

Table 7 reveals the relative contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment with student with visual impairment in Oyo State.

These independent variables constitute the potent predictors of academic adjustment on student with visual impairment in Oyo State. The result shows that there is a significant relative contribution of peer group influence ($\beta = .855$; $t = 6.581$; $P(.000) < 0.05$), and there is a significant relative contribution of parental support ($\beta = .360$; $t =$

2.462; $P (.040) < 0.05$) to academic adjustment with student with visual impairment in Oyo State. As this result reveals, the most potent predictor is peer influence followed by

parental support respectively. This implies that parental support and peer influence have significant relative contributions to academic adjustment on student with visual impairment in Oyo State. Thus, there is significant relative contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment with student with visual impairment in Oyo State.

Discussion

The results of the research question one implies that there was significant the relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment of student living with visual impairment in Oyo State. The result thus matched with that of McConnell and Savage (2015) who investigated the relationship between parental support and academic outcomes among students with disabilities, including those with visual impairment. The findings revealed that students who received consistent emotional, financial, and educational support from their parents demonstrated better academic adjustment, higher self-esteem, and increased motivation in their studies. The study also emphasized that parental advocacy for their children's educational rights positively influenced school performance.

Similarly, Kim and Park (2017) who conducted a longitudinal study on the effects of parental involvement on the academic resilience of students with visual impairment. Their research highlighted that student whose parents actively engaged in their learning processes—such as assisting with homework, attending school meetings, and seeking specialized educational resources—tended to exhibit higher levels of academic persistence and achievement. The study further noted that parental emotional support played a protective role against academic stress and feelings of isolation, thereby enhancing overall adjustment to school life.

Brown and Johnson (2016) examined the role of peer relationships in the academic adaptation of students with visual impairment. Their findings indicated that students who had supportive peer networks exhibited higher levels of academic engagement and confidence in classroom activities. The research highlighted that peer support enhanced motivation, facilitated access to academic resources, and improved emotional resilience.

The results of the research question two stated that there was significant there is significant joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State. Result support the finding of Hadley (2019) found that the experiences of visually impaired college students and the role of parental encouragement in their transition from high school to higher education. The results indicated that students who received substantial parental guidance in navigating academic challenges, learning assistive technologies, and advocating for accommodations at school reported a smoother transition and greater academic success compared to their peers with minimal parental involvement.

Moreover, result was in line with finding of Adeyemi and Ojo (2020) who found that effects of parental socioeconomic status on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The study found that students from financially stable families had greater access to learning materials, assistive technologies, and specialized support services, which significantly contributed to their academic performance. Conversely, students from lower-income backgrounds faced difficulties in acquiring necessary learning aids, which negatively impacted their academic adjustment.

Result correlate the finding of Ahmed and Bello (2019) found that effects of peer mentoring programs on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. Their research demonstrated that structured peer mentorship significantly contributed to the academic success of these students by providing guidance, emotional support, and effective coping strategies for academic challenges. The study emphasized that mentorship programs facilitated knowledge sharing and helped visually impaired students navigate educational environments more effectively.

Furthermore, Okonkwo and Adewale (2020) affirmed that the role of peer influence in the educational aspirations of students with visual impairment. Their study revealed that students who had academically motivated peers were more likely to develop positive attitudes toward learning and set higher academic goals. On the other hand, negative peer influence, such as association with disengaged peers, was linked to lower academic motivation and increased dropout risks.

The results of the research questions three, stated that there was there is significant relative contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment with student with visual impairment in Oyo State. Result correlate with the finding of Garcia and Smith (2021) found that the coping strategies of students with visual impairment and how parental support influenced their academic engagement. Their study revealed that parental encouragement and adaptive support mechanisms, such as teaching self-advocacy skills and fostering independence, played a vital role in helping students adapt to academic challenges. Overall, empirical evidence suggests that parental support—whether in the form of emotional encouragement, academic guidance, financial assistance, or advocacy—significantly enhances the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. Future research should focus on intervention programs that strengthen parental involvement and provide targeted resources to further support these students in their academic journey

Furthermore, result was in line with finding of Rodriguez and Carter (2021) who assessed the impact of peer collaboration on problem-solving skills and classroom participation among students with visual impairment. Their findings suggested that peer-assisted learning approaches, such as cooperative learning groups and study partnerships, significantly enhanced students' cognitive skills, independence, and overall academic adjustment. Overall, empirical evidence underscores the importance of peer influence in shaping the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. Positive peer interactions foster academic motivation, social inclusion, and emotional resilience, while negative peer influences can hinder educational progress. Future research should focus on developing strategies to enhance positive peer interactions and minimize negative peer effects in educational settings for students with visual impairment.

Limitations of the Study

Despite the significance of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. One major limitation is the generalizability of the findings. Since the study was conducted within a specific educational setting in Oyo State, Nigeria, the results may not fully represent students with visual impairment in other regions or different educational contexts. Differences in school policies, cultural attitudes toward disability, and the availability of resources may influence how parental support and peer interactions affect academic adjustment elsewhere.

Another limitation is the self-report nature of data collection. Since students provided information about their own experiences, their responses may have been influenced by personal biases or the tendency to give socially desirable answers. Without direct observation or third-party validation, there is a possibility that some responses did

not fully capture the actual experiences of the participants.

The cross-sectional research design also presents a constraint. By examining the variables at a single point in time, the study does not account for changes in parental support, peer influence, or academic adjustment over time. A longitudinal study would provide deeper insights into how these relationships evolve and whether interventions or changes in family dynamics have long-term effects on students' academic adaptation.

Additionally, the study primarily focused on parental support and peer influence, while other important factors such as teacher support, school infrastructure, government policies, and access to assistive technology were not extensively explored. These elements also play significant roles in academic adjustment and should be considered in future research.

Another challenge was language barriers. Some students, particularly those from rural areas or different linguistic backgrounds, may have had difficulty understanding certain terms or concepts in the questionnaire. Although efforts were made to simplify the language, variations in comprehension could have affected the accuracy and consistency of responses.

The location of the study posed further challenges. Conducting research in multiple schools required coordination with school administrators, and differences in accessibility, school policies, and availability of special education resources may have influenced the results. Some schools had better facilities and more inclusive learning environments than others, which might have shaped how students responded to questions about their academic experiences.

Lastly, data collection constraints due to the nature of visual impairment required special considerations. The questionnaires were provided in Braille or electronic formats, and in some cases, assistance was given to students in completing them. While necessary for accessibility, this may have introduced external influence on how students responded to certain questions.

These limitations highlight the need for further research that addresses these constraints to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment.

Suggestion for Further studies

Future studies can go in several directions to improve our understanding of strong parental involvement, encouraging positive peer interactions, stakeholders can ensure that students with visual impairment receive the necessary support to adjust academically and reach their full potential. While a mixed-methods approach can offer a more thorough knowledge, perception and parental support and peer influence as correlate of academic adjustment among students with visual impairment in Oyo State, longitudinal studies can be used to evaluate changes in inclusive education accessibility over time. Furthermore, analyzing the effects of other factors, like parental socioeconomic position and educational background, could provide insightful information. Finding best practices and possible areas for improvement can be aided by comparative studies conducted across nations or regions. A more inclusive and equitable school environment can also result from assessing the efficacy of measures meant to inclusive education and broadening the focus to include different forms of students with visual impairment.

Conclusion

This study investigates parental support and peer influence on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The study reveals that there is significant relationship that exist among parental support, peer influence and academic adjustment

of student living with visual impairment in Oyo State. It was also established that there is significant joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Oyo State. The also reported that there is significant joint contribution of parental support and peer influence to the academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in Oyo State.

Recommendations:

- (i) Educational institutions should foster collaborative relationships between parents and educators to promote academic adjustment among students with visual impairments. Regular meetings, progress reports, and parent-teacher conferences can facilitate open communication and ensure that parents are informed about their child's academic progress. Additionally, educators should provide parents with strategies and resources to support their child's learning at home.
- (ii) Educational institutions should establish peer mentorship programs that pair students with visual impairments with sighted peers who can provide social support, academic guidance, and emotional encouragement. Peer mentors can help students with visual impairments develop essential social skills, build confidence and self-esteem, and enhance their academic adjustment. Regular training and support should be provided to peer mentors to ensure they are equipped to meet the needs of students with visual impairments.
- (iii) Educational institutions should provide family-centered interventions that address the unique needs of students with visual impairments and their families. These interventions can include counseling, parent support groups, and adaptive technology training. Family-centered interventions can help parents develop the skills and confidence needed to support their child's academic and social development, ultimately enhancing their child's academic adjustment.

Conflict of interest: None.

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